

LANGUAGE CHANGE: DIFFERENT FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE IT

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In this article the problem of language changes had been researched, the authors deal with phonological changes of Latin language to Germanic languages

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All languages change as speakers adopt or invent new ways of speaking and pass them on to other members of their speech community. Language change happens at all levels from the phonological level to the levels of vocabulary, morphology, syntax, and discourse. Even though language change is often initially evaluated negatively by speakers of the language who often consider changes to be "decay" or a sign of slipping norms of language usage, it is natural and inevitable.

Changes may affect specific sounds or the entire phonological system. Sound change can consist of the replacement of one speech sound or phonetic feature by another, the complete loss of the affected sound, or even the introduction of a new sound in a place where there previously was none. Sound changes can be conditioned in which case a sound is changed only if it occurs in the vicinity of certain other sounds. Sound change is usually assumed to be regular, which means that it is expected to apply mechanically whenever its structural conditions are met, irrespective of any non-phonological factors. On the other hand, sound changes can sometimes be sporadic, affecting only one particular word or a few words, without any seeming regularity. Sometimes a simple change triggers a chain shift in which the entire phonological system is affected. This happened in the Germanic languages when the sound change known as Grimm's law affected all the stop consonants in the system. The original consonant *b^h became /b/ in the Germanic languages, the previous *b in turn became /p/, and the previous *p became /f/. The same process applied to all stop consonants and explains why Italic languages such as Latin have p in words like pater and pisces, whereas Germanic languages, like English, have father and fish.

Another example is the Great Vowel Shift in English, which is the reason that the spelling of English vowels do not correspond well to their current pronunciation. This is because the vowel shift brought the already established orthography out of synchronization with pronunciation. Another source of sound change is the erosion of words as pronunciation gradually becomes increasingly indistinct and shortens words, leaving out syllables or sounds. This kind of change caused Latin mea domina to eventually become the French madame and American English ma'am.

This kind of changes we can see in Turkic languages which had great influence from Arabic and Persian languages, In Arabic language the consonant pronounced more strictly for example sound 'k' in Arabic language pronounced in back space of the mouth and tongue, but in Uzbek it pronounced on the front space of the mouth

Some change happened in grammar also. This occurred when words or morphemes limited or disappeared and other language compensate this lost. For example, in some varieties of Caribbean Spanish the final /s/ has eroded away. Since Standard Spanish uses final /s/ in the morpheme marking the second person subject "you" in verbs, the Caribbean varieties now have to express the second person using the pronoun tú. This means that the sentence "what's your name" is ¿como te llamas? ['komo te 'jamas] in Standard Spanish, but ['komo 'tu te 'jama] in Caribbean Spanish. The simple sound change has affected both morphology and syntax. Another common cause of grammatical change is the gradual petrification of idioms into new grammatical forms, for example, the way the English "going to" construction lost its aspect of movement and in some varieties of English has almost become a full-fledged future tense (e.g. I'm gonna).

These changes are the result of integration of different nations and their coexisting in one region. This factor has historical and political impacts to the people's life style.

In conclusion, we can say that language changed and developed in different situations and its priorities many people gives their stylistic colour to other languages.

References:

1. Yuldosheva. G Diplomatiik konsullik huquqi.
2. Cooper, M. & Powell, M. (2009). The New York Times: Politics. Article retrieved on Jan 2, 2012 from <http://www.nytimes.com/2008/10/17/us/politics/17webplumber.html>
3. Duffy, J. (2003). BBC news: Google calls in the "language police." Article retrieved on January 10, 2012 from http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/uk_news/3006486.stm
4. Finegan, E. & Rickford, J. (2004). Language in the USA: Themes for the Twenty-first Century. NY: Cambridge University Press.
5. Kulick, D. (1994). Language shift and cultural change. Paper presented at La Trobe University, Australian Linguistic Institute on language maintenance and shift. Victoria, Australia.